

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BAWA****FIRST NAME: EDWARD ABAMBIRE****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 13%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What should the introduction of a research paper typically include?

- A statement about a flaw or gap in relevant sources
- An answer to the question "So what?"
- The answer to your research question is your claim
- All of the above¹**

2. How should you handle critical concepts in your paper?

- By using different words for them each time
- By avoiding repeating them

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, and the University of Chicago Editorial Staff, Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 111.

- By using specific terms repeatedly to refer to them²**
- By only mentioning them in the conclusion
3. In the author-date citation style, what detail is essential for citing an electronic journal article accessed through a database?
- The DOI or the URL, if a DOI is not available³**
- The name of the database and the URL of the journal's homepage
- The date of access and the database name
- The digital library name and the article's abstract
4. When is it appropriate to use a shortened note in the context of notes-bibliography style?
- When referencing a previously cited source for which you have already provided a complete note⁴**
- Only when citing a source for the first time
- Whenever a source does not have an identifiable author
- For every citation, avoid repetition
5. When should a period be placed at the end of items in a vertical list?

² Turabian, 71.

³ Turabian, 233.

⁴ Turabian, 163.

- When the items are complete sentences⁵**
 - When the items are incomplete sentences
 - When the list is horizontal
 - Regardless of whether the items are complete sentences
6. Why must a dissertation's discussion chapter integrate findings with the literature reviewed in Chapter 2?
- To demonstrate the relevance of findings within the context of existing knowledge⁶**
 - To repeat the content for emphasis
 - To introduce new topics not covered in the dissertation
 - To meet the page requirement set by the university
7. What is the primary purpose of including appendices in a dissertation?
- To provide copies of resources used for replication or extension by other researchers⁷**
 - To fulfill academic requirements for dissertation formatting
 - To add supplementary information that is tangentially related to the research
 - To document the researcher's reflections on the dissertation process

⁵ Turabian, 316.

⁶ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 56.

⁷ Sampson, 64.

8. Using the English Style Guide, how should large numbers be represented in a financial document that requires figures and words?
- By spelling out the numbers fully, including commas and 'and' before the tens or ones in each group⁸**
 - By using figures only, without spelling out the numbers
 - By using a mix of figures and words based on clarity
 - By always using words for numbers in financial documents
9. What is the primary purpose of academic essays?
- To provide answers to hypotheses based on evidence⁹**
 - To express personal opinions without evidence
 - To describe events without analysis
 - To persuade readers to take a specific action
10. What is plagiarism?
- Using the words or ideas of someone without giving credit¹⁰**
 - Citing all sources correctly in a paper
 - Paraphrasing a source accurately
 - Writing a paper independently without any sources

⁸ Tim Cooper et al., eds., *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth Edition (European Union, 2021), 36.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.